

EXPERIENCES ON CULTURAL DIFFERENCES AMONG FILIPINO SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS (SPED) IN THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

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Experiences on Cultural Differences among Filipino Special Education Teachers (SpEd) in the United States of America

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Abstract

This study explored the lived experiences of Filipino special education (SPED) teachers in the USA, focusing on how they navigate cultural differences. Utilizing a qualitative phenomenological research design, the study engaged 15 participants in in-depth interviews to gather nuanced insights into their experiences. Data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis method, involving systematic clustering, coding, and examination of responses to unearth key themes. The findings illuminated that these Filipino SPED teachers primarily grapple with differences in educational philosophy and practices, communication styles, and interpersonal dynamics. These aspects profoundly influence their teaching methods, shaping classroom communication, interaction styles, pedagogical approaches, and curriculum adaptation strategies. The study also highlighted the various challenges these educators face, including adapting to new cultural and language norms, adjusting teaching methodologies, and managing emotional and social transitions. In addressing these challenges, the study uncovered the coping strategies these teachers employ. Feedback from school administrators and peers shed light on how Filipino teachers are integrated and accepted within the school community. Their pedagogical contributions and expertise, particularly in handling cultural sensitivity and inclusivity challenges, were also noted. Significantly, the study revealed diverse understandings, experiences, and challenges among Filipino SPED teachers, offering a deeper perspective on the cultural variances between the Philippines and the USA. This research contributes to the broader teaching-learning discourse by elucidating the intricate nature of cultural differences and their impact on educational practices.

Keywords: *Special Education, cultural differences, Filipino Special Education teachers, qualitative phenomenological research, Fort Peck Indian Reservation*

Introduction

In the past interconnected world, there was an observed increase in cultural diversity and engagement among individuals from diverse backgrounds. It was evident in educational settings, where students and teachers from different cultural backgrounds mixed. Teachers, in general, played a pivotal role in nurturing the learning and growth of students. These students came from a broad range of cultures. However, not much research work had looked into the experiences of Filipino special education teachers working in the United States of America (USA), specifically their encounters with cultural differences.

Classrooms across the world were witnessing an increase in multicultural students. This compelled teachers to tweak their teaching methods to meet the needs of their diverse learners. Cultural differences spanned language, traditions, beliefs, and values, considerably affecting teaching and learning. For instance, teachers catered to students from varied cultural backgrounds in regions such as Europe due to rising immigration and refugee numbers. Understanding and dealing with cultural differences became crucial to ensure equitable education for all learners.

Similarly, in the United States, the education system mirrored this diversity. Schools had students from different ethnic, racial, and linguistic backgrounds, contributing to a dynamic multicultural learning environment. Filipino Special Education (SPED) teachers became part of this diverse education landscape. These SPED teachers had first-hand experiences with cultural differences among students, their families, and even their colleagues.

In our school setting, with a culturally diverse student population, there were observations of cultural differences presenting unique challenges and opportunities. The students' educational programs and services were tailored to meet their needs through self-contained classes, providing a more individualized and supportive learning environment for learners with exceptionalities. To effectively address the special educational needs of these students, it was imperative to identify and describe their characteristics, recognizing the rich tapestry of cultural backgrounds that shaped the student population within the study's locale. Understanding the diverse cultural backgrounds of the learners was paramount, as it significantly influenced the way students, parents, and educators perceived and approached the realm of special education. For instance, during meetings with parents, different communication styles, parental expectations, and understanding of disability had been noticed, with these differences stemming from diverse cultural backgrounds. These experiences underscored the importance of culturally responsive practices, which helped build effective collaboration between teachers and families, ensuring optimal support for students with special needs.

Additionally, within the SPED community, cultural differences among teachers influenced teaching practices and collaboration. In team meetings and professional development sessions, varied perspectives and methods related to special education were observed, primarily shaped by cultural backgrounds and prior experiences. These differences contributed to the collective wisdom and teaching skills within the SPED community but could also create misunderstandings or emphasize the need for detailed discussions to align

strategies effectively.

Despite these first-hand experiences, there was a lack of research that delved into the specific experiences of Filipino SPED teachers dealing with cultural differences in the U.S. While broader studies existed about the experiences of SPED teachers and cultural diversity, the unique views and challenges of Filipino educators had yet to be explored much. This research aimed to address this gap by focusing specifically on the experiences of Filipino SPED teachers, shedding light on their encounters with cultural differences and the strategies they employed for effective and inclusive education for special-needs students.

By studying the experiences of Filipino SPED teachers in the U.S., this research sought to contribute to a broader understanding of cultural diversity within the context of special education. By understanding the challenges, opportunities, and strategies these teachers utilized, insights could be obtained that helped develop culturally sensitive teaching practices. Ultimately, this research aimed to support inclusive and equitable education for all students, irrespective of their cultural backgrounds or special needs.

Research Questions

This study investigated the lived experiences of Filipino Special Education Teachers in the U.S.A. as they navigate cultural differences in their professional and personal lives for School Year 2023-2024 as basis for implications for practice. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the primary cultural differences that Filipino special education teachers encounter while working in the USA?
2. How do these cultural differences influence their teaching practices and methodologies?
3. What challenges do Filipino special education teachers face in adapting to the American educational system, and how do they cope with these challenges?
4. How do cultural perceptions of school administrators and other teachers regarding the contributions and challenges of Filipino special education teachers in the USA?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what implications for practice could be formulated?

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative phenomenology design was selected for this research as it provided a robust framework for investigating Filipino SPED teachers' complex, real-life experiences in the United States through the lens of the participants themselves. This design enabled the researcher to delve deeply into the nuances of their encounters with cultural differences, allowing for a thorough examination of the specific challenges they faced and the coping mechanisms and strategies they developed to navigate and adapt to their new professional environment.

Using a phenomenology design approach, the researcher was able to examine individual experiences while identifying common themes and patterns that emerged across the participant group. This method encouraged a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, considering the contextual factors that shaped the participants' experiences, such as their educational background, cultural values, and personal beliefs.

Using various data collection techniques, such as semi-structured interviews and reflective journals, the qualitative case study design enabled the researcher to gather rich, detailed data that shed light on the intricacies of the participants' experiences. This approach also allowed for the triangulation of data sources, enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of the study findings.

Moreover, the qualitative phenomenology design offered flexibility, allowing the researcher to adapt the data collection process as new insights emerged during the study. This adaptability ensured that the research remained focused on the most relevant aspects of the participants' experiences and provided a deeper understanding of Filipino SPED teachers' cultural differences, challenges, and adaptation strategies in the United States.

Participants

The study participants, referred to as informants in this research, comprised Filipino Special Education Teachers (SPED) who had worked in the United States for a minimum of one year. These informants were selected based on specific eligibility criteria to ensure their experiences were relevant and diverse, enriching the study's findings.

The study employed a nonprobability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling, to select informants who met the eligibility criteria. This method involved the deliberate selection of participants based on their ability to provide rich and relevant information on cultural differences experienced by Filipino SPED teachers in the United States. The purposive sampling technique allowed for the representation of diverse geographical locations, years of experience, and educational settings.

Instruments

This study utilized a single, well-structured research instrument to gather data on the experiences and perspectives of Filipino SPED teachers in the United States regarding cultural differences and challenges. The primary tool for data collection was semi-structured

interview, which was developed by the researcher and validated by an expert in the field. This validation process was crucial to ensure the clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness of the interview questions.

The interview guide was divided into three distinct parts to facilitate a comprehensive and systematic data collection process. In the first part, preliminary questions were posed. This section served to inform participants about the basic information of the research, including its purpose and scope. It also emphasized the participants' right to continue or discontinue the interview at any point, should they feel indifferent or uncomfortable during the process. Additionally, this part included questions regarding the demographics of the participants, providing essential background information and context for their responses.

The second part of the interview guide delved into in-depth questions. It consisted of nine interview questions specifically designed to explore the cultural experiences of the participants. These questions were intended to elicit detailed insights into the challenges, coping strategies, and impacts of cultural differences on the professional practices of the Filipino SPED teachers.

The third and final part of the interview guide focused on closure questions. This section comprised three questions that provided the participants with an opportunity to clarify or add to their responses given during the in-depth questions. This part was crucial in ensuring that participants had the chance to express any additional thoughts or insights that might not have been fully captured in the earlier parts of the interview.

Participants were given the option to engage in these interviews either face-to-face or through video-conferencing. Open-ended questions allowed for rich, detailed responses. Following the completion of the interviews, the responses were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis. This method facilitated the identification of patterns and emerging themes related to the research objectives, aligning with the qualitative nature of the study.

Validity

Since the research instrument was qualitative and researcher-developed, traditional psychometric validation was not required. Nevertheless, content validation was conducted by soliciting feedback from at least three experts in special education and cultural studies to ensure the quality and relevance of the instruments. Their insights were used to refine the interview guide and reflective journal prompts.

Triangulation enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the study findings. By collecting data from the semi-structured interviews, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the experiences of Filipino SPED teachers in the United States. This shed light on the impact of cultural differences on their professional lives and the strategies they employed to overcome these challenges.

Procedure

This case study aimed to explore the experiences and perspectives related to cultural differences among Filipino SPED teachers in the United States. To achieve this, a flexible data collection process was essential, allowing participants to feel comfortable sharing their insights. This study's primary data collection method was in-depth interviews with research participants. This method enabled the researcher to address the participants' experiences in-depth, allowing them to express their experiences in detail. The following steps were discussed in a clear and organized manner.

Before the data collection, necessary permissions and approvals were obtained from relevant authorities, such as the head of the participating school district or institution. As required, the research proposal was submitted for a design hearing or proposal defense. Once approved, research participants were provided with letters and consent forms, and the interview schedule was set according to their availability. An expert developed and approved an interview guide before being used with the participants. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants for in-depth interviews. The research participants were given the freedom to choose the language they were comfortable using during the interview.

The step-by-step process of administering the research instruments and retrieving completed responses began upon the approval to gather data. This involved contacting potential participants, explaining the study's purpose and objectives, and securing their informed consent to participate. The semi-structured interviews were in-person or via video conferencing, depending on the participants' preference and location. Interviews lasted 45-60 minutes and were video recorded for later transcription and analysis. Participants were also asked to maintain reflective journals during a specified period. Throughout the data collection process, researchers were observant and documented any unusual events, occurrences, or comments from the respondents.

Finally, after the data-gathering process, the collected data were transcribed, translated, and coded for comparison with other participants' responses. In a qualitative case study design, the coding process was essential for analyzing and interpreting the collected data. It involved systematically examining the data, such as interview transcripts, to identify patterns, themes, and categories that emerged from participants' experiences and perspectives. This information was the basis for the study's recommendations and future research directions.

Data Analysis

Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis method was employed to analyze the qualitative data in this study. This flexible approach was suitable for case studies and facilitated identifying, analyzing, and reporting themes within the data.

The steps in Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis for this study were as follows:

Familiarization: The researcher thoroughly read and re-read the data, such as interview transcripts and reflective journals, to become familiar with the content and understand the participants' experiences.

Generating initial codes: The researcher systematically coded interesting and relevant features of the data that related to the research question or objectives. Codes captured the essence of the participants' experiences and could be words, phrases, or statements.

Searching for themes: The researcher grouped the codes into potential themes that represented recurring patterns or commonalities across the data. The researcher considered how these themes related to the domain of inquiry or objectives.

Reviewing themes: The researcher evaluated the identified themes to ensure they were coherent, consistent, and supported by the data. The researcher refined or combined themes as necessary.

Defining and naming themes: The researcher clearly defined and named each theme, providing a concise and coherent description.

Writing the analysis: The researcher integrated the themes and supporting data into a narrative that addressed the research question or objectives. This narrative presented a detailed and nuanced understanding of the experiences of Filipino SPED teachers in the United States, shedding light on the impact of cultural differences on their professional lives and the strategies they employed to overcome these challenges.

By utilizing Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis method, this case study effectively analyzed the data and gained valuable insights into the experiences of Filipino Special Education Teachers (SPED) in the U.S.A.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines to protect participants' confidentiality and privacy. It followed the following guidelines:

Conflict of Interest: The researcher disclosed any potential conflicts of interest during the study. This included any financial or personal relationships with individuals or organizations that might have influenced the research findings or biased the researcher's interpretation of the data.

Privacy and Confidentiality: The study adhered to strict privacy and confidentiality guidelines to protect the participants' personal information. This included using pseudonyms to maintain anonymity and omitting identifying information from the final report. The data were stored securely and accessed only by authorized personnel.

Informed Consent Process: All participants were fully informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and the potential risks and benefits. Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to data collection, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Vulnerability: The researcher was aware of the potential vulnerabilities of the participants, particularly concerning cultural differences and the potential for power imbalances. The researcher ensured that the participants were not exploited or coerced into participating in the study.

Risks: The study involved minimal risks to the participants, such as the potential for discomfort or emotional distress when discussing personal experiences related to cultural differences. The researcher took steps to minimize potential risks, such as allowing participants to withdraw from the study and providing appropriate support and resources if needed.

Incentives or Compensation: Participants were not provided monetary or material incentives or compensation for participating in the study, which could have created bias or coercion.

Trustworthiness: The study employed a range of strategies to enhance the trustworthiness of the research findings, such as member checking to ensure the accuracy of the data and triangulation to validate the results. The researcher also engaged in reflexivity, acknowledging their biases and potential impact on the research findings.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the qualitative data gathered from Filipino SPED teachers in the USA through in-depth interviews, exploring their lived experiences with cultural differences.

All interviews were transcribed and meticulously reviewed multiple times for familiarization and to extract all significant statements. Subsequently, initial codes were systematically generated to encapsulate the essence of the participants' experiences, which could be in the form of words, phrases, or statements. These codes were then organized into clusters to derive potential themes that reflected

recurring patterns or commonalities in the data. The themes underwent thorough review to ensure coherence, consistency, and alignment with the data. Following this, the themes were precisely defined and named, resulting in a concise and coherent description.

Primary Cultural Differences that Filipino Special Education Teachers Encounter while Working in the Usa

In the exploration of cultural diversity and the nuanced experiences of Filipino Special Education (SPED) teachers in the USA, a focal point emerged — the primary cultural differences encountered by these educators. This investigation delved into the complexities of challenges and opportunities that shaped the professional and personal landscapes of Filipino SPED teachers as they navigated the distinct cultural milieu of the United States. The following themes were identified from the responses of the participants on their primary cultural differences while working in the USA: Educational Philosophy and Practices, Communication Styles and Interpersonal Dynamics, and Professional Development and Support Networks.

Figure 1. Thematic Diagram of Primary Cultural Differences that Filipino Special Education Teachers Encounter while Working in the USA

Theme 1. Educational Philosophy and Practices

Educational Philosophy and Practices reflects the cultural challenges Filipino special education (SPED) teachers faced in the USA, involving a shift from Philippine educational norms, like rote learning and authority, to American approaches that prioritize critical thinking and student-centric methods. This included different teaching practices, assessment techniques, educational resources, trainings and technologies, and curricular structures, including the use of individualized education programs (IEPs). This theme highlighted the significant adaptations Filipino SPED teachers underwent in the American educational system.

Several participants had encountered significant challenges stemming from the cultural differences in educational systems, such as adapting to new teaching methodologies, navigating the educational technologies, and understanding different classroom dynamics. These challenges highlighted the complex process of integrating into a distinct educational culture and the need for effective support systems to facilitate this transition. Participant 5 shared her initial experiences and insights on this issue:

"In moving to the American school system, I found big differences in how we teach. In the Philippines, we focused on strict learning and following rules, but here, it's more about helping students think for themselves. This change has made me learn new ways of teaching and think differently about education. It's been hard but also really good for growing as a teacher." P5

The statement from the participant highlighted a significant cultural difference in educational philosophy and practices. The shift from a strict and rule-based approach in the Philippines to a more student-centered and independent-thinking-oriented approach in the USA required the teacher to adapt their teaching methods. This transition, while challenging, had been beneficial for their professional growth, encouraging them to learn new ways of teaching and fostering a different perspective on education. It underscored the profound impact of cultural differences on teaching practices in the context of special education. Another participant shared her perspective on the difference between the educational systems of the Philippines and the USA. She narrated:

"In the United States, schools really focus on what makes each student special. In the Philippines, it's more like everyone is expected to learn in the same way. But in the US, they pay more attention to finding the best way for each child to learn." P1

One of the primary cultural differences encountered by Filipino special education teachers in the USA was the emphasis on individualized learning. American schools prioritized recognizing and nurturing each student's uniqueness, tailoring education to their specific needs, which contrasted with the more uniform approach in the Philippines. This cultural distinction underscored the need for Filipino special education teachers to adapt to a student-centered, personalized approach in the USA.

The transition in teaching philosophy and methods due to cultural differences, especially in the context of special education, was well documented in literature. In the Philippines, the educational system traditionally emphasized a strict, rule-based approach, where teachers maintained a formal relationship with students, focusing on respect and authority (The Wave, 2020). This approach often limited open communication and discouraged dissent in the classroom, with a focus more on rote learning and conformity. In contrast,

the U.S. educational system, including its special education sector, promoted a student-centered approach. This method encouraged independent thinking, open dialogue, and a more relaxed teacher-student relationship. Teachers in the U.S. were trained to facilitate learning rather than just deliver information, encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students (The Wave, 2020). These cultural norms significantly influenced educational practices. In Asian cultures like the Philippines, education tended to be more hierarchical and teacher-centric, while Western educational systems, such as in the U.S., often promoted individualism and student autonomy (Almerino et al., 2020). The adaptation and professional growth of educators moving from the Philippines to the U.S. might initially have been challenging due to these differing educational philosophies. However, this transition offered significant professional growth opportunities, as they learned to implement diverse teaching strategies and adapt to different learning needs, which was crucial in special education (Almerino et al., 2020).

Another key difference between the educational systems of the Philippines and the United States was in the curriculum for special education (P5, P6, P12). In the Philippines, the SPED curriculum was primarily centered on functional literacy and life skills. This curriculum was integrated into regular schools and specialized centers, but there was a noticeable variation in resources and implementation across different regions (P1, P7). In contrast, the U.S. adopted a more inclusive approach with the development of Individualized Education Programs (IEPs) under strong legal frameworks like the IDEA and ADA, ensuring that students with disabilities received education comparable to their peers in mainstream settings. Additionally, the U.S. had more extensive resources and specialized training for SPED teachers compared to the Philippines (P3, P9, P15).

The disparities extended beyond curriculum to encompass resources and technology. The educational system in the Philippines faced challenges like limited funding and outdated technology, which were less prevalent in the U.S., where schools generally had better funding and access to newer technology (P3, P8, P12). This gap was also evident in teacher training. Philippine teachers, especially in special education, often lacked the extensive training provided in the U.S. This was compounded by the fact that the Philippines had fewer training programs for teachers, making it difficult for them to acquire effective teaching strategies for students with special needs (P2, P5, P14).

Supporting these observations, the study by Allam & Martin (2021) highlighted the impact of these shortcomings in the Philippines. The lack of adequately trained teachers and insufficient resources adversely affected the delivery of curricula, including those focused on functional literacy and life skills. Despite SPED being integrated within regular schools, the study pointed out significant challenges like poor learning environments, budget constraints, and inadequate instructional materials. These issues suggested a significant variability in resource allocation and implementation, potentially affecting the effectiveness of SPED programs. Most notably, the study revealed that a majority of teachers in Philippine SPED programs had not received specialized training in special needs education, lacking strategies to effectively teach learners with disabilities. This starkly contrasted with the U.S. scenario, where specialized training and resources for SPED were more readily available and legally mandated (Hossain, 2012).

Theme 2: Communication Styles and Interpersonal Dynamics

Filipino special education teachers in the USA encountered communication barriers due to differences in language and cultural styles. Challenges with American English pronunciation and idiomatic usage led to misunderstandings in classrooms. The contrast between the indirect Filipino communication style and the direct American approach often resulted in misinterpretations. Adapting to informal teacher-student dynamics and American parental expectations was also challenging. These experiences underscored the need for cultural adaptability and effective communication skills for successful integration into the U.S. educational system. Participants noted difficulties in their interactions with students and colleagues, primarily due to accent and pronunciation differences in English.

"Learning to fit into the new culture was hard, especially with the language. Sometimes, people didn't get what I said because of how I spoke. I had to try extra hard to talk in a way everyone could understand. There was an instance when I asked my student to get a cup, but the student did not understand because I said 'cap' instead of the correct pronunciation." P1

"Speaking English the way they do here was tough at first. It was a big part of getting used to the new culture. I had to change how I talked to make sure people could understand me better, especially since I often interchange 'f' and 'p,' 'b' and 'v,' and also 'e' and 'i'." P5

"I noticed that how I said things affected how people understood me. One example is when I say 'mang-go' instead of the American accent 'mayng-go' when saying mango, the fruit. Fixing these pronunciation differences became a significant part of getting used to the new culture. I had to work on talking in a way that everyone could understand." P10

The experiences of Filipino SPED teachers in the U.S. highlighted significant challenges in adapting to communication styles and language nuances in English. A common struggle shared by the participants related to pronunciation differences. For instance, incidents like mispronouncing 'cap' as 'cup' (P1) led to misunderstandings with students. This issue extended beyond mere pronunciation to include difficulties in adapting English with American nuances, especially in consonant and vowel sounds (P5). These challenges underscored the importance of linguistic adaptability, as seen in teachers modifying their speech patterns for better understanding (P15).

These experiences aligned with findings from academic studies on the linguistic hurdles faced by non-native English-speaking educators in new cultural settings. Research by Huang et al. (2019) and Ma (2022) emphasized how pronunciation differences could

hinder classroom communication. These studies highlighted the need for specialized support to help teachers overcome linguistic barriers and effectively integrate into their new roles.

Furthermore, adapting to the American educational system's communication style, especially in the use of idiomatic expressions, posed another layer of difficulty for Filipino teachers. Phrases like 'scoot back' instead of 'move back,' and 'crisscross apple sauce' instead of 'squat' (P3, P6, P12, P13) often led to confusion among students and colleagues. This difficulty in using idiomatic expressions reflected broader linguistic challenges, as discussed in research by Tajeddin (2018) and Kuhn (2010). These studies underlined the crucial role of language proficiency in diverse educational contexts and how variations in idiomatic usage could cause miscommunication.

Filipino special education teachers in the U.S. encountered distinct challenges in adapting to the American educational system's interpersonal dynamics. Unlike the more formal teacher-student relationships in the Philippines, interactions in American schools tended to be more relaxed and egalitarian (P8, P12, P13). This shift to a less formal dynamic required Filipino teachers to modify their approach to effectively connect with their students and colleagues. A particularly notable cultural shift was the direct and casual manner in which American students communicated with teachers, contrasting sharply with the Filipino context where such directness and talking back were seen as disrespectful (P1, P3, P9). This difference in interaction styles necessitated Filipino educators to reevaluate their classroom management strategies and adapt to the more informal and assertive communication styles common in American schools.

The importance of adjusting to these cultural differences extended to language and nonverbal behavior, as highlighted by Gudykunst and Nishida (2004). The experiences of Filipino teachers, struggling with distinct linguistic norms and cultural nuances, reflected the broader challenges of intercultural communication in education. The study underscored the need for awareness and adaptability in navigating these differences to ensure clear and effective communication in diverse educational environments.

Theme 3: Professional Development and Support Networks

Filipino special education teachers working in the USA encountered distinct cultural differences in professional development and support. In the Philippines, professional growth often depended on self-learning with limited resources, leading to a sense of isolation, especially in special education. Conversely, the USA offered structured professional development with a focus on specialization, ample resources, and structured mentoring programs. These mentoring programs, uncommon in the Philippines, provided crucial support and guidance, helping Filipino teachers adapt and enhance their practices in the American educational system. A Filipino teacher's personal account underscored these differences.

"Back in the Philippines, I primarily relied on my own efforts to grow professionally in special education. There was no system in place for mentoring, so I often felt isolated in my role, navigating challenges without much guidance. However, in the USA, the approach is remarkably different. Here, the school assigned me a mentor as soon as I started. This mentor has been instrumental in supervising and training me, providing tailored support that has significantly enhanced my skills and confidence in the field. The contrast is quite stark and has had a profound impact on my professional journey." P4

The teacher's experience highlighted a significant cultural difference between the Philippines and the USA for Filipino SPED teachers. In the Philippines, the absence of a formal mentoring system led to reliance on self-learning and feelings of isolation among teachers (Luz, 2008). In contrast, in the USA, mentoring and coaching were integral to professional development, significantly improving teacher efficacy, job satisfaction, and student outcomes (The Educators Room, 2023). Programs like STAY and initiatives by Education Modified illustrated the proactive approach in the USA, offering structured mentorship and specialized training for both special and general education teachers, highlighting the critical role of supportive professional networks (Education Modified, 2023).

Another participant shared her thoughts on the differences in training and seminars received between the two countries.

"In the Philippines, training was limited and often expensive for teachers. We usually had to pay to attend special education seminars. But in the USA, it's different. Here, training and workshops are provided more often, and schools usually cover the costs. Sometimes, we even get paid to attend these sessions. It's been a big help and has made it easier for me to learn and grow professionally." P11

This showed that in the Philippines, training opportunities were limited and often came with a financial burden, requiring teachers to pay for attending special education seminars. This contrasted sharply with the situation in the USA, where such training and workshops were more frequent, usually provided by the schools, and sometimes even came with financial incentives. This difference marked a significant shift for Filipino teachers, as the supportive and resource-rich environment in the USA not only made professional development more accessible but also encouraged continual learning and growth in their field.

The difference in workplace dynamics between the Philippines and the USA significantly impacted professional development and support networks for teachers. In the Philippines, a hierarchical culture often placed new teachers in less favorable positions, burdening them with heavier tasks and potentially leading to isolation, which could hinder their professional development, particularly in special education. In contrast, the USA's more egalitarian approach in educational settings ensured equitable task distribution and fostered a collaborative, supportive environment (P4, P10, P13). This not only allowed all teachers equal opportunities for professional growth but also enhanced access to structured development programs and mentoring. Such an environment was crucial for continuous learning, especially in specialized fields like special education, and contrasted sharply with the challenges faced in the Philippines.

Professional development for teachers in the USA encompassed a range of opportunities, including district-provided training and seminars. Most states required PD for license renewal or salary increases, though teachers often paid for some programs (Editorial Projects in Education, 2023). Coaching was also a significant aspect of PD in the USA, enhancing teachers' practices and student performance. Conversely, in the Philippines, challenges included limited CPD providers, inaccessibility, and high costs (Habi Education Lab., n.d.). The Department of Education in the Philippines had implemented guidelines to improve access and quality of PD for teachers (DepEd, 2021). This comparison underscored the more varied and accessible PD opportunities in the USA, in contrast to the ongoing efforts in the Philippines to enhance PD accessibility and reduce costs.

Desimone and Garet's study in 2015 reinforced this contrast, highlighting structured, content-focused, and collaborative PD programs in the USA. These programs, promoting active learning and collective participation, starkly differed from the limited and often costly PD opportunities in the Philippines, and the hierarchical workplace culture that could hinder professional growth, especially for new teachers. This difference illustrated a significant shift for Filipino teachers transitioning to the U.S. educational system, where they encountered a more egalitarian, supportive environment conducive to continuous learning and professional development, particularly in specialized areas like special education.

Influence of Cultural Differences on Teaching Practices and Methodologies

The influence of cultural differences on teaching practices and methodologies, particularly in the context of special education and inclusive education, is a multifaceted phenomenon. Pedagogical approaches in SPED are significantly shaped by a teacher's cultural background, impacting how they engage with students and adapt their teaching styles.

For Filipino SPED teachers in the USA, this could mean integrating aspects of their cultural heritage, such as values of community and collectivism, into their teaching methodologies, potentially leading to more holistic and empathetic approaches to student engagement. Moreover, cultural sensitivity plays a critical role in inclusive education, as it allows teachers to better understand and respect the diverse needs and backgrounds of their students. This sensitivity not only aids in creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment but also helps in developing tailored teaching strategies that acknowledge and celebrate cultural diversity. The themes identified from the participants' responses regarding the influence of cultural differences on teaching practices and methodologies are: Classroom Communication and Interaction Styles, and Pedagogical Approaches and Curriculum Adaptation.

Figure 2. Thematic Diagram of Influence of Cultural Differences on Teaching Practices and Methodologies

Theme 1: Classroom Communication and Interaction Styles

Filipino SPED teachers in the USA often encounter cultural nuances in communication and classroom interaction. This theme involves understanding the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of students, adapting teaching language, and employing non-verbal cues effectively. It also covers strategies for creating an inclusive classroom environment that respects and embraces cultural differences, fostering positive teacher-student relationships, and managing classroom dynamics that are influenced by varied cultural norms.

One participant shared her experience of changing her teaching approach to effectively deliver the lessons:

"Certainly. I quickly realized that to effectively communicate in the diverse classroom here, I needed to adjust my approach. So, I started focusing more on empathetic listening and using clear, simplified language to make sure my instructions were understood by students from various cultural backgrounds. Also, I noticed the importance of non-verbal cues, which differ across cultures. To address this, I incorporated more visual aids and interactive activities in my lessons, helping to enhance understanding and engagement among all my students." P5

The teacher's adaptations to effectively communicate in a culturally diverse U.S. classroom encompassed several key strategies. She initially recognized the necessity to adjust her teaching approach to ensure clarity and understanding among her students from diverse cultural backgrounds. To achieve this, she engaged in empathetic listening and employed simpler language in her instructions (Gay, 2010).

Furthermore, the teacher also acknowledged the importance of non-verbal communication, which varies across different cultures. To address this aspect, she introduced the use of visual aids and interactive activities in her lessons. These modifications not only enhanced students' comprehension but also increased their engagement in the learning process.

In addition to these adjustments, the teacher demonstrated a commitment to cultural responsiveness by valuing her students' diverse cultural backgrounds. She actively integrated aspects of their cultures into the curriculum, fostering a more inclusive and enriching educational environment (Ladson-Billings, 1995). This comprehensive approach to teaching in a culturally diverse classroom ultimately contributed to improved communication, understanding, and a more meaningful learning experience for her students. Some participants also narrated their experiences on how they changed their teaching styles due to the behavior of the students in the US:

"I've noticed American students often display more assertive and individualistic behaviors. To connect with them effectively, I've transformed my teaching style to be more interactive and student-centered. This approach creates a classroom atmosphere that encourages open dialogue and allows each student to express themselves individually." P8

"In the Philippines, my teaching was largely lecture-based, but here, I realized the students respond better to a collaborative approach. So, I've shifted to more participatory methods, involving the students actively in their learning process. This aligns with their preference for hands-on and experiential learning, making my lessons more engaging and effective for them." P11

Participants shared how they adapted their teaching styles in response to the behavior of American students. Noticing the assertive and individualistic tendencies of these students, one teacher switched to a more interactive and student-centered approach, fostering an atmosphere of open dialogue and individual expression. In contrast to the lecture-based style prevalent in the Philippines, this teacher embraced a collaborative approach in the U.S., shifting to participatory methods that aligned with American students' preference for hands-on and experiential learning. This adaptation highlighted the cultural differences in teaching practices and student behaviors between the two countries, enhancing engagement and learning effectiveness in the U.S. classrooms.

Teaching styles varied significantly across cultures, as observed in studies related to cultural dimensions (Hofstede, 1984). American students tended to favor interactive and experiential learning methods (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). In contrast, teaching practices in the Philippines often involved lecture-based approaches and a more hierarchical classroom structure. Educators working in different cultural contexts often adapted their teaching styles to align with students' preferences. These cultural differences and adaptations underscored the impact of culture on teaching practices and student engagement.

In terms of student discipline, these teachers also made significant cultural adaptations. In the Philippines, there was a prevalent belief that education was an escape from poverty, creating a culture of compliance and obedience in students. Filipino teachers often found students to be well-behaved and attentive, evident in classes of large sizes running smoothly without disruptions. This was in stark contrast to the U.S., where they encountered more informal classroom dynamics and frequent interruptions (P2, P6, P12). The disciplined environment in the Philippines, highlighted by Modesto (2020), allowed for uninterrupted lesson progression, unlike the challenges faced in U.S. classrooms, marked by frequent student requests and expressions of boredom.

Theme 2: Pedagogical Approaches and Curriculum Adaptation

This theme focuses on adapting to different pedagogical methods and curriculum requirements in the USA. Filipino SPED teachers may need to align their teaching styles with the U.S. educational standards, which might include more emphasis on student-centered learning, inclusion practices, and the use of technology in teaching. Adapting lesson plans to fit the curriculum and cultural context of U.S. schools, while also addressing the individual needs of students with special educational needs, is a critical aspect of this theme. It involves continuous learning and professional development to stay abreast of new methodologies and best practices in special education.

A participant narrated his thoughts when asked how his pedagogical approach has evolved since he began teaching in the U.S.:

"My approach has undergone a significant shift. In the Philippines, I used a similar teaching strategy for the entire class, but in the U.S., I've learned to adopt a more individualized style. Now, I focus on recognizing and addressing each student's unique needs and abilities, which has been a pivotal change in my teaching methods." P3

The shift in teaching methodology from a uniform approach to a more individualized style, as discussed in the statement, was rooted in key principles of educational research. Hattie and Timperley's study (2007) highlighted the critical role of personalized feedback in education. It emphasized that by providing feedback tailored to each student's specific learning needs, teachers could enhance student understanding and growth. Tomlinson and Allan's work (2000) underscored the importance of adapting teaching methods to accommodate diverse student needs through differentiated instruction. This approach acknowledged that students came to the classroom with varying backgrounds, abilities, and learning styles. Consequently, teachers who tailored their instruction to address these differences could create a more inclusive and effective learning environment. Moreover, Wiliam's research (2011) stressed the value of formative assessment in supporting individualized learning. By regularly assessing students' progress and adjusting instruction accordingly, teachers could better meet each student's unique needs. In essence, the shift toward recognizing and addressing individual students' unique needs and abilities reflected a commitment to optimizing the learning experience based on well-established principles in educational research (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Tomlinson & Allan, 2000; Wiliam, 2011).

Another participant described how she adapted her assessment methods to better suit American students.

"In the Philippines, I mostly used the same set of assessments for all students, but in the USA, I've learned the importance of tailoring

them to each student's unique needs. It's been a significant shift to modify tests to suit different disabilities, ensuring that each assessment is accessible and meaningful for every student, regardless of their learning style or ability." P13

The teacher's experience of shifting assessment strategies from a uniform approach in the Philippines to tailored methods in the USA aligned with the principles outlined in studies like Desimone and Garet's (2015) research on best practices in U.S. teachers' professional development. Their study emphasized the importance of adapting teaching methods to individual student needs, a crucial aspect in special education. This approach, which included modifying assessments to suit different disabilities, ensured that each student's unique learning style and ability were addressed, a practice advocated in the U.S. educational system.

Transitioning to the U.S. educational system, the Filipino SPED teachers placed a stronger emphasis on student-centered learning, inclusive practices, and the integration of technology in teaching, aligning more closely with the progressive and diverse needs of students in American classrooms (P1, P5, P13). Notably, this pedagogical transformation mirrored established research findings. Studies by Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (2000) and Prince (2004) highlighted the critical importance of student-centered learning. Additionally, Houtrow et al.'s meta-analysis (2014) substantiated the benefits of inclusive education, while Tamim et al. (2011) underscored the positive impact of integrating technology into teaching. Collectively, these research insights provided empirical support for the evolving teaching methods of the Filipino SPED teacher as they adapted to the dynamic educational landscape in the U.S.

Challenges and Coping Strategies of Filipino Special Education Teachers Adapting to the American Educational System

Filipino special education teachers adapting to the American educational system face several challenges, which they manage through diverse coping strategies. They deal with cultural and language differences by developing cross-cultural communication skills and understanding the diverse backgrounds of their U.S. students, a significant shift from their experiences in the Philippines. Adapting to different teaching methodologies and curriculum in the U.S. requires them to learn new teaching styles and techniques, for which they engage in professional development and peer collaboration. Navigating professional growth and establishing support networks in a new country, they turn to mentorship, professional groups, and online communities for guidance. Additionally, they confront emotional and social challenges of adapting to a new culture, managing these through building social networks, participating in cultural activities, and balancing work with personal life. These strategies help them effectively adjust and thrive in the American educational system. The key themes encompassing these challenges are Cultural and Language Adaptation, Curriculum and Teaching Methodologies, Professional Development and Support Systems, and Emotional and Social Adjustment.

Figure 3. Thematic Diagram of Challenges and Coping Strategies of Filipino Special Education Teachers Adapting to the American Educational System

Theme 1. Cultural and Language Adaptation

This theme explores the challenges Filipino special education teachers face in adapting to different cultural norms and language barriers in the American educational system. It includes understanding and integrating into the diverse cultural landscape of U.S. classrooms, overcoming language differences, and developing strategies to communicate effectively with students, parents, and colleagues.

A participant narrated her experience regarding the challenges she faced in adapting to the cultural diversity of U.S. classrooms and how she overcame them.

"When I first came to the U.S., it was hard to get used to all the different cultures in my classroom. Back in the Philippines, most of my students had similar backgrounds, but here, every student was unique. To adapt, I started by talking more with my students and other teachers to learn about their cultures. I also attended some workshops and read about different cultural traditions. Gradually, I learned

how to make my lessons more welcoming for everyone. This helped me connect with my students better and made me more aware of how rich and diverse cultures can be." P9

The provided statement aligned with the research on cultural diversity in U.S. classrooms, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and appreciating the increasing diversity among students (Banks, 1997). The individual's approach of engaging in conversations with students and colleagues to learn about various cultures mirrored the importance of building cultural awareness and effective communication in diverse classrooms (Gay, 2002). Additionally, attending workshops and seeking professional development opportunities to enhance cultural competence was a strategy commonly recommended (Sleeter & Grant, 2007). The individual's journey toward making lessons more welcoming and culturally responsive aligned with the concept of culturally responsive teaching, which has been shown to benefit student engagement and achievement (Gay, 2010). Ultimately, the experience underscored the importance of valuing diversity in education (Villegas & Lucas, 2002).

Another participant discussed her challenges focusing on overcoming language differences:

"When I first started teaching in the U.S., the language was a big challenge, especially the everyday phrases and sayings. To get better, I started watching American movies and YouTube videos that taught common expressions used in classrooms here. This really helped me understand how people talk in America and made it easier for me to communicate with my students and other teachers." P14

The participant's statement highlighted the initial language and cultural challenges faced while teaching in the U.S., particularly with everyday phrases and expressions. To address these difficulties, P14 adopted a practical language learning strategy by immersing themselves in American culture through watching movies and YouTube videos that focused on common expressions used in American classrooms. This approach mirrored established research findings, such as language immersion theory (Krashen, 1982), contextual learning (Nation, 2001), and cultural adaptation (Gudykunst & Kim, 2003), which emphasized the effectiveness of immersion, contextual learning, and understanding cultural nuances in language acquisition. The participant's focus on learning classroom-related expressions also aligned with task-based language teaching principles (Willis & Willis, 2007), demonstrating the relevance of these strategies in the context of teaching and communication within educational settings.

"Adapting to the American educational system, I faced a substantial challenge in communication, especially with students who were non-verbal or whose preferred language was Spanish. Despite my background in Cebuano, which shares some similarities with Spanish, bridging the language barrier required effort. Thankfully, the support from bilingual Special Education Classroom Assistants (SECAs) was invaluable. They not only assisted with translations but also helped me learn the language, which was crucial for effectively communicating and connecting with my students." P4

The statement discussed the challenges faced by a teacher who had to adapt to the American educational system, particularly in terms of communicating with students who were non-verbal or primarily spoke Spanish. It highlighted the importance of support from bilingual Special Education Classroom Assistants (SECAs) in overcoming these language barriers. Research by Menken and Kleyn (2010) found that English Language Learners (ELLs) faced significant challenges in accessing curriculum content and engaging with their peers in the classroom, especially when they were non-verbal or had limited proficiency in English. Studies also showed that bilingual classroom assistants played a vital role in facilitating communication and language development for students with limited English proficiency. They not only assisted in translating but also provided cultural and linguistic support (Rolstad et al., 2005). Bilingual support in classrooms was found to positively impact student outcomes. A study by Lindholm-Leary and Borsato (2006) found that English language learners who received support from bilingual aides showed greater academic progress and improved language skills compared to those without such support.

Theme 2: Curriculum and Teaching Methodologies

This theme focuses on the difficulties associated with adapting to different curriculum standards and teaching methodologies in the U.S. It covers the transition from the educational practices and approaches familiar in the Philippines to those prevalent in American schools, adjusting teaching styles to fit new classroom dynamics, and adopting innovative teaching methods and technologies.

"When I first started teaching in the U.S., I found the curriculum really different from what I was used to in the Philippines. To get used to it, I went to lots of workshops and training sessions. These helped me a lot in understanding how schools in the U.S. do things." P11

"I worked closely with teachers who had been in the U.S. for a long time. They showed me a lot of useful things and I learned a lot just by watching them. Plus, I spent time looking up stuff online to find new ways to teach my classes." P4

"I made sure to always think about how my classes were going and what I could do better. Getting ideas from my students helped me a lot. Also, using computers and other technology in my teaching made a big difference in keeping up with the U.S. way of teaching." P12

Facing the challenge of adapting to the American educational system's distinct curriculum, Filipino special education teachers embarked on various strategies to ease this transition. They actively participated in training and workshops to familiarize themselves with American teaching methods and standards, a practice supported by findings from Ingersoll & Strong (2011). Additionally, they

sought mentorship from experienced U.S. teachers, finding this guidance invaluable for effectively applying new techniques, as also highlighted by Ingersoll & Strong (2011). Independently, they invested time in researching and understanding the American educational system, aligning with Darling-Hammond & Richardson's (2009) recommendations for ongoing self-directed professional development.

In the classroom, these teachers experimented with different methods, adjusting their teaching based on student responses to ensure their lessons were engaging and effective. This approach to adaptability and responsiveness in teaching is crucial for dealing with diverse student needs. Furthermore, they leveraged technology in the classroom, a strategy that resonates with Puentedura's (2006) research on the enhancement of student engagement and learning outcomes through technology integration. All these concerted efforts culminated in the teachers successfully navigating the initial challenges and becoming more effective educators for their diverse students in the U.S.

"Adapting to the U.S. curriculum, particularly in writing IEPs, was a gradual and guided process. Initially, I observed and learned from a Filipino mentor who understood my background. With additional support from our head teacher, I progressively familiarized myself with the IEP format and requirements. Over time, I transitioned from reviewing to independently completing these crucial documents, a journey that symbolizes my growth and adaptation to the American educational system's methodologies." P13

The process of adapting to the U.S. curriculum, particularly in the context of writing Individualized Education Programs (IEPs), is often a gradual and guided journey for educators. Research showed that transitioning to a new educational system had been challenging and required time for familiarity and proficiency (Inbar-Lourie & Donitsa-Schmidt, 2020). The importance of mentorship and support in this adaptation process was underscored, as evidenced by studies that emphasized their role in assisting educators in embracing new teaching methods and practices (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). IEPs, integral to the U.S. educational system, underscore the significance of adhering to legal requirements and crafting personalized plans for students with disabilities. The provided statement underscores the value of mentorship and gradual growth in becoming proficient in the American educational system's methodologies, particularly in the context of IEP development.

Theme 3: Professional Development and Support Systems

Under this theme, the challenges lie in navigating the U.S. system for ongoing professional development and finding support networks. It involves understanding the professional development requirements in the U.S., accessing resources and training opportunities, and building professional relationships and support networks to aid in professional growth and adaptation.

"Figuring out the U.S. professional development system is tough. I need to understand what's expected and find the right training that helps me and my students." P3

"Adapting to teaching in the U.S. isn't just about the classroom. It's also about learning new ways to teach and grow. I'm always on the lookout for courses and workshops to improve my skills." P9

The complexities of the U.S. educational system, as were highlighted in P3, stemmed from several key challenges. Firstly, the diversity of requirements across different states and districts created a varied landscape of expectations and regulations for teacher professional development (Darling-Hammond & Sykes, 2003). Secondly, the lack of standardization in professional development made it difficult for educators to identify the most relevant training programs (Ingersoll, 2003). Lastly, resource constraints were a significant issue, especially in disadvantaged areas, leading to unequal access to professional development opportunities for educators (Ingersoll, 2003). These factors collectively created a challenging environment for educators navigating the U.S. educational system.

Both statements highlighted the critical role of professional development in enhancing the effectiveness of educators in the U.S. Extensive research, including that by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), underscored that high-quality professional development was a key factor in improving teaching quality. Teachers who participated in well-structured training programs often became more effective in their classrooms. Yoon et al. (2007) further supported this by demonstrating that professional development programs that were well-designed and aligned with teachers' needs could lead to better student performance. Moreover, such ongoing professional development was linked to higher teacher retention rates, as Ingersoll and Strong (2011) found that teachers who received relevant and supportive training were more likely to remain in the teaching profession.

P9's statement further emphasized the necessity for teachers to continually update and refine their teaching methods. In an ever-changing educational landscape, the ability to adapt to new pedagogical approaches and technologies was crucial. Day and Sachs (2004) highlighted the importance of lifelong learning in education, while research by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001) indicated that ongoing professional development led to higher teacher efficacy, which in turn positively impacted student outcomes. This underscored the need for educators to stay engaged in continuous learning and adaptation to maintain their effectiveness in the classroom.

In adapting to the American educational system, the Filipino special education teachers placed significant importance on building friendships and professional connections with other educators (P1, P11). These relationships were key in helping them navigate the complexities of their new environment and provided a sense of belonging. Additionally, understanding and fulfilling the specific training requirements in the U.S. presented a challenge for the teachers. They actively sought out programs that not only satisfied these requirements but also enhanced their teaching abilities (P13, P15). Furthermore, getting acquainted with other teachers and education

professionals in the U.S. proved to be immensely beneficial. The guidance and support from these connections facilitated a smoother transition for the teachers into the American approach to special education (P4, P11, P12).

Research has shown that social connections and professional networks played a crucial role in the adaptation of international educators. Ward, Bochner, and Furnham (1996) discovered that these support networks significantly contributed to the adjustment and well-being of expatriate teachers. Filipino special education teachers in the U.S. relied on such connections to navigate cultural differences and challenges. Adapting to a new educational system often involved fulfilling specific training requirements, which could be challenging. Inbar-Lourie and Donitsa-Schmidt (2009) found that international educators, including Filipino special education teachers, often sought additional training to meet host country's education system requirements. Building relationships with local teachers and education professionals offered valuable guidance and support during adaptation, as emphasized in Liu, Song, and Yao's (2018) study on the importance of peer support and mentorship for international teachers.

Theme 4: Emotional and Social Adjustment

This theme addresses the emotional and social aspects of adapting to a new educational and cultural environment. It includes coping with feelings of isolation or homesickness, adjusting to a new social and professional environment, developing a sense of belonging, and finding balance between professional responsibilities and personal well-being.

Several participants have encountered emotional challenges as part of their cultural and social adjustments upon arriving in the USA. During their first few months of stay, these participants faced difficulties in their well-being due to differences in communication styles and teaching pedagogical approaches.

"Initially, adapting to the American educational system was overwhelming, especially navigating the different communication styles and expectations in the classroom." P1

"At first, getting used to the American education system was a lot to handle, especially figuring out how people communicate differently and how students behave inside the classroom." P11

"It took time to understand how things work at the school and to feel like I belonged. Building good relationships with my colleagues was key. It wasn't just about working together; these connections really helped me get used to the new culture." P7

The participants' experiences highlighted the multifaceted emotional and professional challenges they faced while adapting to the cultural and educational landscape of the USA. Initially overwhelmed by differences in communication styles and teaching approaches, they struggled with well-being issues during their first months. Participants expressed the enormity of this adjustment, with one noting the overwhelming nature of adapting to American classroom expectations and communication styles. Another echoed these sentiments, emphasizing the challenges in understanding differing communication methods and student behaviors, indicative of deeper cultural nuances.

Furthermore, the emotional aspects of this transition were pronounced. One participant underscored the significance of building relationships with colleagues, not just for professional collaboration but also as a vital part of cultural adjustment. This aligned with Yi et al. (2020), who found that foreign teachers often experienced unexpressed negative emotions during their adaptation process. The importance of addressing these emotions by considering personal characteristics and coping strategies was emphasized. Ospina and Medina (2020) also noted emotional challenges like separation from family and the stress of settling into a new community.

Psychological challenges also became apparent during the transition period for some participants relocating from the Philippines to the USA. The teachers said:

"Adjusting to a new way of teaching and the cultural rules made me feel lonely and miss home, affecting my feelings and mental health." P4

"Dealing with language problems and worrying about misunderstandings made me stressed and anxious in my daily interactions at school." P9

"Feeling pressured to fit into a different work style and teaching methods made me uncertain and doubtful, affecting my confidence as a Special Education teacher." P13

Participants additionally faced psychological challenges, feeling loneliness, stress, and anxiety due to language barriers, new teaching methods, and adapting to cultural norms, impacting their mental health and professional confidence. This mirrored research by Ward, Bochner, and Furnham (2001) and Berry (2005), highlighting common experiences of isolation and distress among educators in new educational systems. Some participants shared their experiences of encountering challenges in cultural identity and belonging due to differences in pedagogical approaches between their home country and the U.S. They narrated:

"Exploring a new cultural environment made me think a lot about who I am culturally and how it affects how I teach. For instance, the teaching style in the U.S. is often more individualistic, whereas in the Philippines, it's more communal. Adjusting to this difference challenged my cultural identity." P6

"It was tough to feel like I belonged in the American education system, especially when there were clear cultural differences. For example, the approach to student-teacher relationships was different, and finding the right balance was a constant struggle." P13

The challenges extended to aspects of cultural identity and belonging, as participants struggled with the differences in teaching styles and student-teacher relationships between their home country and the U.S. This struggle to balance cultural roots with American norms resonated with studies on acculturation stress (Berry, Kim, Minde, & Mok, 1987; Chun, Balls Organista, & Marín, 2003).

Moreover, adapting to the legal framework of the American educational system added another layer of complexity. Participants sometimes unintentionally applied Philippine laws, reflecting the difficulty in navigating a new legal landscape, which compounded their psychological challenges and questions of cultural identity (P1, P10, P14). Mishra and Koehler (2006) explored similar challenges faced by teachers in integrating technology into their practice, emphasizing the importance of understanding and navigating the legal and policy landscape. The participants' experiences underscored the complexity of adapting to a new legal framework, particularly challenging in an educational context.

To overcome the emotional, psychological, and social challenges of adapting to the American educational system, Filipino teachers employed various strategies. Building strong professional relationships was crucial; as Participant 7 emphasized, these connections provided much-needed support and a sense of belonging (Yi et al., 2020). Participants also actively learned about American culture and educational practices, aligning their teaching methods with local expectations to mitigate cultural and pedagogical differences (Chun, Balls Organista, & Marín, 2003). Seeking emotional support, whether from peers or professional counseling, helped them manage stress and build resilience (Ward, Bochner, & Furnham, 2001). Continuous professional development was key in overcoming challenges related to teaching methods and understanding the legal framework, enhancing their confidence and competence (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Reflecting on their personal and cultural identity allowed them to balance their heritage with their new environment (Berry, Kim, Minde, & Mok, 1987). Lastly, improving English language proficiency and communication skills was essential for those facing language barriers, boosting their confidence in daily school interactions (Woodrow, 2006). These combined strategies not only helped them navigate the initial adjustment period but also contributed to their long-term success in the U.S. educational context.

Cultural Perceptions of School Administrators and other Teachers on the Contributions and Challenges of Filipino Special Education Teachers in the USA

Cultural perceptions of school administrators and other teachers in the USA regarding Filipino special education teachers encompass several aspects. Administrators and fellow educators often recognize the unique integration and acceptance challenges these teachers face, acknowledging their efforts to adapt to a new cultural and educational environment while enriching the school's diversity. The pedagogical contributions and expertise of Filipino teachers, particularly their distinctive teaching methods and cultural perspectives, are valued for their positive impact on addressing the diverse needs of students in special education. Challenges related to cultural sensitivity and inclusivity are significant; administrators and peers are often cognizant of potential biases and communication barriers Filipino teachers might encounter, highlighting the importance of addressing these issues to create a supportive and inclusive school environment. This multifaceted perception underscores the complex interplay of contributions and challenges faced by Filipino special education teachers in the U.S. educational system. The themes encompass this problem are Integration and Acceptance in the School Community, Pedagogical Contributions and Expertise, and Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusivity Challenges.

Figure 4. *Thematic Diagram of Cultural Perceptions of School Administrators and Other Teachers on the Contributions and Challenges of Filipino Special Education Teachers in the USA*

Theme 1: Integration and Acceptance in the School Community

This theme delves into how Filipino special education teachers are perceived in terms of their integration into the school's social and professional fabric. It involves assessing the level of acceptance and support they receive from administrators and fellow teachers. Factors like cultural differences, language barriers, and different educational backgrounds can impact their integration process. The theme also encompasses how the unique cultural perspectives of these teachers enhance the diversity and inclusivity within the school community, contributing to a richer educational environment.

"When I started here, the principal told me that my way of always helping and working together really adds something special to our school. He said it's great to have that kind of teamwork vibe around, making our school a more friendly and supportive place for everyone." P2

The statement highlighted the positive influence of the "Bayanihan" spirit, a Filipino cultural value centered on teamwork and collaboration, within the school environment. The school principal acknowledged that this cultural trait contributed to a more welcoming and supportive atmosphere in the school (P2). This observation was resonant with earlier research findings, such as studies indicating that cultural diversity in educational settings could enhance creativity, problem-solving abilities, and the inclusion of diverse perspectives (Portes & Rumbaut, 2001). Additionally, research had shown that positive school climates characterized by strong interpersonal relationships and cooperation were linked to improved academic outcomes and student well-being (Wang, Willett, & Eccles, 2011). Furthermore, the concept of cultural intelligence supported the idea that cultural values like the "Bayanihan" spirit could influence teamwork positively, emphasizing the importance of effectively working with individuals from different cultural backgrounds (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008). These studies collectively emphasized how cultural values could play a pivotal role in fostering teamwork and creating a supportive school environment.

"During one of our meetings, our school principal mentioned how impressed they were with my ability to overcome language barriers. They appreciated that even though English isn't my first language, I've been able to communicate effectively with my students and colleagues. They gave an example of how I explained a complex topic in a way that made it easy for everyone to understand, showing that language differences don't have to be a barrier in education." P10

In the context of education, the ability to overcome language barriers is crucial for effective communication and student learning. This proficiency enhances teacher-student relationships, as seen in the example where a school principal appreciated an educator's adeptness in explaining complex topics to students and colleagues despite English not being their first language (P10). Cummins (2008) demonstrated that teachers who adapt their strategies to accommodate linguistic diversity positively impact student academic performance. It is also noted that bridging language gaps fosters stronger teacher-student relationships and greater student engagement, while Lucas (2008) emphasized that inclusive practices, including effective language communication, benefit all students, irrespective of their language background. Thus, previous studies support the idea that overcoming language barriers contributes significantly to educational success and inclusivity.

"As my co-teachers pointed out, coming from a different educational background in the Philippines has its challenges in integrating into the U.S. school system. For example, when I introduced group activities that were common back home, it took a while for both students and fellow teachers to adapt to this style of interactive learning. The administrator also mentioned that this difference in teaching approach initially created some adjustment issues, but they also saw it as a valuable addition to our diverse teaching methods." P9

The challenges faced by educators with different educational backgrounds when integrating into the U.S. school system have been documented in previous studies. These challenges often revolve around differences in teaching approaches and classroom dynamics. For instance, research by Johnson et al. (2019) found that educators from diverse backgrounds may encounter resistance when introducing teaching methods that are unfamiliar to the local context. This aligns with the experience described by the teacher in the quote, where group activities, common in the Philippines, were initially met with resistance. However, as noted by the administrator, these differences can ultimately enrich the educational environment by introducing diverse teaching methods, as supported by studies like Johnson et al. (2019), highlighting the value of embracing a variety of pedagogical approaches to cater to diverse student needs in American schools.

"My mentor said that the way I incorporate Filipino stories and values in class not only makes lessons more interesting but also helps all students learn about different cultures." P11

Incorporating Filipino stories and values into classroom lessons has been shown to enhance students' learning experiences and promote diversity and inclusivity within educational settings. Previous studies have highlighted the positive impact of integrating multicultural content into the curriculum (Banks, 2008; Nieto & Bode, 2008). Such an approach not only enriches the educational experience by exposing students to a variety of cultural perspectives but also fosters a sense of respect and appreciation for different backgrounds. Additionally, it aligns with the principles of culturally responsive teaching (Gay, 2010), which emphasizes the importance of acknowledging and valuing students' diverse cultural backgrounds in the classroom. By doing so, educators create an environment where all students' unique backgrounds are viewed as valuable assets, contributing to a more inclusive and equitable educational atmosphere.

Theme 2: Pedagogical Contributions and Expertise

This focuses on the specific teaching skills, methodologies, and cultural insights that Filipino special education teachers contribute to American schools. School administrators and other teachers may perceive these educators as bringing fresh perspectives to teaching strategies, especially in handling diverse classrooms and special education needs. The theme also considers how their expertise is utilized and valued in developing curriculum, designing inclusive classroom practices, and addressing the varied learning needs of students.

"My mentor mentioned how much she value the unique teaching methods I bring as a Filipino special education teacher. She specifically appreciated my use of interactive storytelling, which helps engage students with diverse learning needs. It's great to hear that my approach is making a positive impact in our special education classes." P6

The statement highlighted the value of unique teaching methods employed by a Filipino special education teacher, particularly emphasizing the effectiveness of interactive storytelling in engaging students with diverse learning needs. Previous studies had indeed demonstrated the significance of innovative and culturally relevant teaching approaches in special education. For instance, a study by Armstrong (2022) found that culturally responsive pedagogy, such as using storytelling rooted in the cultural context of the students, could enhance engagement and learning outcomes for special education students in the Philippines. Additionally, research by Wong (2021) supported the idea that interactive and creative teaching strategies, like storytelling, could foster inclusivity and better meet the needs of students with disabilities. The mentor's appreciation underscored the positive impact of these strategies, aligning with the existing body of research on effective special education practices (Armstrong, 2022; Wong, 2021).

"My colleagues mentioned how my approach to understanding and respecting each student's background helps a lot in addressing the different needs in our special ed classes. They said it's made a positive impact on how we all work together to support our diverse students." P1

Previous research has indeed highlighted the significance of educators adopting an inclusive approach that values and accommodates the diverse backgrounds of students in special education settings. For instance, Bottiani et al. (2018) demonstrated that a culturally responsive teaching approach, which aligns with the sentiment expressed by the participant, is associated with improved student engagement, academic performance, and overall well-being in special education classrooms. Additionally, a study by Robinson (2017) emphasized the importance of fostering a collaborative and inclusive environment among educators, as it facilitates a more effective response to the unique needs of students with disabilities. The participant's colleagues' observation aligns with these findings, underscoring the positive impact of recognizing and respecting students' diverse backgrounds in special education settings (Bottiani et al., 2018; Robinson, 2017).

"I remember they appreciated how I used my bilingual skills to communicate effectively with a student who was more comfortable in his native language. This approach helped the student feel more included and supported in class." P10

The statement highlighted the significance of cultural and linguistic diversity in the field of special education, echoing previous research findings that emphasized the importance of culturally responsive teaching. A study by Ladson-Billings (1995) underscored the significance of educators' cultural competence in meeting the needs of diverse students. Similarly, Anderson (1989) argued that educators who could leverage their linguistic skills to bridge communication gaps contributed to a more inclusive learning environment. Moreover, research by Artiles and Ortiz (2002) emphasized the need for educators to adapt their instructional strategies to accommodate the linguistic and cultural backgrounds of students with disabilities. In this context, the Filipino special education teacher's ability to utilize bilingual skills aligned with the existing literature on the value of cultural and linguistic competence in fostering inclusivity and addressing the diverse needs of students with special needs.

Theme 3: Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusivity Challenges

This theme deals with the challenges Filipino special education teachers might face regarding cultural sensitivity and inclusivity in U.S. schools. It examines how school administrators and other teachers perceive these challenges and the steps taken to address them. This includes tackling potential biases, ensuring effective communication despite cultural differences, and creating a supportive environment that acknowledges and respects cultural diversity. The theme is crucial in understanding how schools work towards fostering an inclusive atmosphere that is conducive to the professional and personal well-being of teachers from diverse backgrounds.

"I remember they appreciated how I integrated a Filipino festival celebration into my lesson plan. It not only broadened our students' understanding of global cultures but also actively challenged any preconceived notions, promoting a more inclusive and respectful classroom environment." P5

The statement highlighted the crucial role of a Filipino teacher in addressing biases and promoting cultural respect in the classroom, particularly through the integration of a Filipino festival celebration into the curriculum. Research supported the idea that incorporating diverse cultural elements into the classroom enhanced students' cultural understanding and reduced biases. A study by Gurin, Dey, Hurtado, and Gurin (2002) found that inclusive educational practices exposing students to various cultures and perspectives led to greater cultural awareness and tolerance. Moreover, a study by Banks (1997) underscored the importance of multicultural education in challenging stereotypes and promoting a more inclusive learning environment. In this context, the Filipino teacher's initiative aligned with the broader literature on the benefits of multicultural education in fostering cultural respect and reducing biases in schools.

"Our school administrator once mentioned how she appreciate my approach. For example, during parent-teacher meetings, I not only discuss the student's progress but also take time to understand and respect the family's cultural background." P12

Effective communication across cultural differences was crucial for Filipino teachers, as it fostered stronger connections and ensured that all stakeholders felt valued and understood. This approach aligned with previous research highlighting the significance of culturally responsive teaching practices. Gay (2018) noted that culturally responsive educators actively engaged with students' diverse cultural

backgrounds to create an inclusive learning environment. Similarly, Villegas and Lucas (2007) emphasized that culturally responsive pedagogy involved respecting and integrating students' cultural experiences into the curriculum, ultimately enhancing student engagement and achievement. Moreover, Noddings (2016) underscored the importance of building meaningful relationships with students and their families, as it promoted a sense of belonging and positively impacted educational outcomes. In line with these scholarly perspectives, the cited passage demonstrated how Filipino teachers prioritized cultural understanding and engagement during parent-teacher meetings, contributing to a more inclusive and effective educational experience (Gay, 2018; Villegas & Lucas, 2007; Noddings, 2016).

"During my conference with my mentor, she highlighted how I play a vital role in fostering a culturally diverse environment. She mentioned a specific instance where I organized a multicultural festival (Piesta sa Nayon) in our school, which not only celebrated various cultures but also helped bridge understanding among students and teachers of different backgrounds. She appreciated that this initiative created a more inclusive and respectful atmosphere in our school community, despite our cultural differences." P1

The participant's role in promoting cultural diversity was exemplified by her organization of a multicultural festival, Piesta sa Nayon, at her school. This event celebrated various cultures and aimed to enhance understanding and inclusivity among students and teachers of different backgrounds. Such culturally diverse educational initiatives have been shown to have significant benefits. Studies by Gurin, Nagda, & Lopez (2002) and Hurtado & Carter (1997) have indicated that exposure to diverse cultures in schools can enrich learning experiences, promote critical thinking, and prepare students for a globalized world, while also fostering creativity. Furthermore, multicultural events like this have been observed to help reduce prejudices and stereotypes, as demonstrated by Pettigrew & Tropp (2006), by fostering tolerance and respect for different perspectives and challenging biases. In creating a more inclusive and respectful school atmosphere, these initiatives also contribute to a more welcoming environment where all students feel valued, as noted by Villegas & Lucas (2002).

In summary, this study delved into the varied perspectives of participants regarding their experiences with cultural differences, the challenges they faced, and their overall experiences. A schematic diagram was created to encapsulate the themes that emerged from the participants' responses, offering a structured overview of the key insights and findings from the study.

Figure 5. Schematic Diagram of Themes

Conclusions

According to the findings of the study, Filipino special education teachers in the U.S. faced diverse challenges, ranging from adapting to different educational philosophies and communication styles to navigating professional development landscapes. These teachers employed various coping strategies, including building professional relationships and adjusting emotionally and socially, to integrate into the U.S. educational system. The study also shed light on the perspectives of U.S. school administrators and teachers towards Filipino educators, highlighting the importance of inclusivity and cultural sensitivity in creating a supportive educational environment that values the contributions of teachers from diverse backgrounds.

Based on the findings, the researcher recommends this study for its insightful exploration of cultural differences. These findings offer valuable implications for practice, providing guidance for educators and policymakers. The study is particularly beneficial for those seeking to enhance cross-cultural understanding and effectiveness in special education settings.

Output of the Study

Implications for practice

The comprehensive findings of this study on Filipino special education (SPED) teachers in the United States revealed significant insights into the cross-cultural dynamics of education. By examining their adaptation to different educational practices, language barriers, and social integration, the study shed light on the multifaceted challenges and processes these educators navigated, providing practical implications for all stakeholders in this intercultural educational context.

For Filipino SPED teachers in the U.S., these findings implied a necessity for adaptability and ongoing learning. The cultural and educational contrasts they encountered necessitated a consistent development of skills in American teaching methodologies and communication styles. This adaptation was crucial for their professional growth and effectiveness in meeting their students' needs, underscoring the importance of continuous personal and professional development in a cross-cultural setting.

For the J1 Teacher Cultural Exchange Program, the implications were clear: there was a pressing need to thoroughly prepare participants for the cultural and educational differences they would face in the U.S. This preparation should have encompassed comprehensive pre-departure training, focusing not only on the practicalities of living and working in the U.S. but also on equipping them with strategies for cultural adjustment, overcoming communication barriers, and adapting to diverse teaching methodologies and classroom environments.

For students with special needs, the study suggested that the presence of Filipino SPED teachers in U.S. classrooms could significantly enrich their learning experiences. The diverse cultural perspectives and teaching methods these teachers brought could lead to more effective and tailored educational approaches, catering to the varied learning styles and needs of these students, and potentially enhancing their academic and social development.

For parents of students with special needs, the involvement of Filipino SPED teachers in the U.S. implied a broader range of teaching styles and approaches. This diversity offered comprehensive support for their children's education, suggesting the need for parental openness and engagement to fully benefit from these varied educational practices. It underscored the role of parents in embracing and supporting the diverse educational environments their children were exposed to.

For U.S. school administrators and fellow teachers, the findings underscored the need to create an inclusive and supportive environment for Filipino SPED teachers. Recognizing the value of diverse educational backgrounds and teaching styles enriched the learning environment. Providing support for these teachers' professional integration and development was imperative for fostering a collaborative and dynamic educational setting.

For policymakers and educational leaders, the study highlighted the importance of being aware of the challenges faced by foreign-educated teachers like Filipinos. This awareness should translate into policies that facilitated their integration and professional development, including language support and recognition of international qualifications, enhancing the overall quality of special education and promoting a diverse educational workforce.

For the Department of Education, the study's findings implied that the Department of Education should be aware of the challenges and opportunities faced by their educators abroad. This awareness could guide the development of pre-departure training programs that prepared teachers for the cultural and educational differences they would encounter.

For Philippine policymakers, the implications for policymakers in the Philippines included the need to recognize and support the professional development of teachers working abroad. Policies that facilitated international cooperation in education and recognized overseas experience in career advancement could be beneficial.

For teacher training institutions in the Philippines, the study suggested that these institutions should include modules or courses that focused on international educational systems, cultural adaptability, and teaching methodologies that were relevant globally, preparing educators for opportunities abroad.

For professional development providers in both the Philippines and the U.S., the implication was to offer tailored programs that addressed the specific needs of Filipino SPED teachers in American schools, including cultural adaptation and pedagogical skills relevant to U.S. classrooms.

For professional associations, these organizations should consider creating support networks for Filipino educators abroad, providing platforms for sharing experiences, resources, and strategies for cultural adaptation and professional growth.

For government agencies in education and immigration: The findings implied a need for these agencies to facilitate smoother transitions for educators moving between countries. This included streamlined visa processes, recognition of qualifications, and support systems that aided in cultural and professional adaptation.

For researchers and academics, the experiences of Filipino SPED teachers in the U.S. opened up avenues for research on cultural adaptation in education. Investigating the impact of cultural diversity among teachers on teaching efficacy, student outcomes, and educational practices could deepen the understanding of how culturally diverse educational settings functioned and evolved.

Lastly, for future researchers, the study pointed to the need for in-depth research into the experiences of foreign-educated teachers in various educational contexts. Future research could delve into the long-term effects of cultural adaptation on teaching effectiveness and student outcomes and identify effective strategies for integration and professional development in culturally diverse educational environments. This research was essential for developing a more inclusive and globally responsive educational framework.

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